

A COMPARISON STUDY IN BODYBUILDERS BY AGE FOR SINGLE TWO LEG JUMP PARAMETERS

**Kukeli, R.,
Skenderi, Dh.**

Sports University of Tirana,
Tirana, Albania

Abstract:

Introduction: The goal of this study was to investigate the difference between three age groups of bodybuilders for jump parameters using single two leg jump test. **Methods:** In this study, three groups of randomly selected subjects were included. 28 participants took part in the study (9 participants 18.5 years SD 2.1; 8 participants 22.7 years SD 2.4; 11 participants 29 years SD 2.9). The participants were regularly bodybuilder that took part in national championship in Albania. Single two leg jump test were used measuring jump parameters. **Results:** The data from the study for comparison between age groups for maximum rate of action do not show significant changes (sig = 0.2), the jump height / min has significant changes (sig = 0.04), the height of the jump did not show significant changes (sig = 0.1), the efficiency of the jump (the power applied to the applied force) does not show significant changes (sig = 0.7), the total of maximum force does not show significant changes (sig = 0.2), the maximum left foot force does not show significant changes (sig = 0.2), the force difference $_{p_t1_t3}$ (sig = 0.3), the total of maximum power does not show significant changes (sig = 0.6), the maximum left foot power does not show significant changes (sig = 0.8), the maximum right foot power does not show significant changes (sig = 0.4). **Discussion:** The study results show that the maximum right foot force has significant changes (sig = 0.04), the maximum force difference between left and right legs is significant (sig = 0.03), the maximum relative strength has significant changes (sig = 0.03).

Keywords: jump, strength, bodybuilder

1. Introduction

Several studies have analyzed how long the fatiguing effects of cardiovascular exercise last. In general with both continuous long duration and interval training there are decrements in maximal strength and the ability to perform repetitions at a submaximal load immediately, 4 hours, and 8 hours post exercise (Leveritt & Abernethy 1999; Sporer & Wenger 2003). But these decrements appear to subside by 24 hours. However,

a previous cardiovascular session, though it does not impede performance, still appeared to change the fiber recruitment response for up to 32 hours. In particular, it appears that at least in trained individuals there is greater plasma concentrations of ammonia which is generally thought to increase in formation as a result of a greater reliance on fast twitch fibers, though it may also indicate greater protein degradation. Data from Widrick et al (1993) show that the second window bodybuilders should be weary of is after exercise. Following training protein synthesis rises within the first hour. In untrained individuals, it peaks at 16 hours but can be maintained for up to 72 hours. The goal of this study was to investigate the difference between three age groups of bodybuilders for jump parameters using single two leg jump test.

2. Methods

In this study, three groups of randomly selected subjects were included. 28 participants took part in the study (9 participants 18.5 years SD 2.1; 8 participants 22.7 years SD 2.4; 11 participants 29 years SD 2.9). The participants were regularly bodybuilder that took part in national championship in Albania. Single two leg jump test were used measuring jump parameters, Leonardo mechanography test (Single Two Leg Jump).

2.1 Statistical analysis

All variables evaluated in this study were tested for normality. The ANOVA (one way) test followed by the LSD (post hoc) test was used to compare the difference between the groups. Level $p < 0.05$ (Significant Change) was accepted in this study. All statistical analyzes were performed using SPSS 20.0 software.

3. Results

Table 1 shows data for the age group of 20 years for the average indicators and the standard deviation of the maximum two-leg jump force. For the category of age -20 years; the performance indicators by weight, (average = 100.9) (SD = 13.6), maximum action speed (mean = 2.6) (SD = 0.2), jump height / min (average = 0.2) (SD = 0.04), jump height (mean = 0.5) (SD = 0.06), the efficiency of the jump (the power applied to the applied force) (average = 80.5) (SD = 11.2), total maximum force (mean = 2.5) (SD = 0.4), maximum left foot force (mean = 1.2) (SD = 0.2), maximum right foot force (mean = 1.2) (SD = 0.2), the maximum force difference between left and right legs (mean = 6.4) (SD = 5.9), maximum relative strength (mean = 3) (SD = 0.4), the force difference $_p_t1_t3$ (mean = 6.6) (SD = 4.1), maximum total power (mean = 4.7) (SD = 0.1), maximum left foot power. (mean = 2.3) (DS = 0.5), maximum right foot power (mean = 2.4) (SD = 0.5), power difference between left-right legs (mean = 6) (SD = 4.7), maximum power per kg (mean = 56.4) (SD = 8.1), the ratio between maximum jump and spin (average = 280.4) (SD = 95.2).

Table 1: Descriptive statistics for test performed on single two leg jump for age -20 yrs

Age_Range		Mean	Std. Deviation
-20 yrs	Single_two_leg_jump_EFI	100.8889	13.58717
	Single_two_leg_jump_V_max	2.6111	.19310
	Single_two_leg_jump_Height_min	-.1767	.04690
	Single_two_leg_jump_Jump_Height	.4622	.06016
	Single_two_leg_jump_Efficensy	80.5556	11.21507
	Single_two_leg_jump_Force_max_total	2.4644	.40050
	Single_two_leg_jump_Force_max_L	1.2367	.21915
	Single_two_leg_jump_Force_max_R	1.2389	.19141
	Single_two_leg_jump_diff_F_max	6.4444	5.87859
	Single_two_leg_jump_Force_max_rel	3.0444	.40057
	Single_two_leg_jump_Force_Diff_p_t1_t3	6.6000	4.15090
	Single_two_leg_jump_Power_max_total	4.7200	.99662
	Single_two_leg_jump_Power_max_L	2.3500	.53068
	Single_two_leg_jump_Power_max_R	2.3811	.47593
	Single_two_leg_jump_Power_diff_P_max	6.0000	4.74368
	Single_two_leg_jump_Power_max_kg	56.7900	8.13498
Single_two_leg_jump_Power_h_max_h_min	280.4222	95.16862	

Table 2 gives data for the age group 20-25 years; performance indicator by weight, (mean = 99) (SD = 16.1), maximum action speed (mean = 2.8) (SD = 0.1), jump height / min (average = 0.3) (SD = 0.09), jump height (mean = 0.5) (SD = 0.04), the efficiency of the jump (the power applied to the applied force) (mean = 82) (SD = 2), total maximum force (mean = 2.3) (SD = 0.3), maximum left foot force (mean = 1.1) (SD = 0.2), maximum right foot force (mean = 1.2) (SD = 0.1), the maximum force difference between left and right legs (mean = 12.7) (SD = 6.9), maximum relative strength (mean = 2.9) (SD = 0.5), the force difference p_{t1_t3} (mean = 6.9) (SD = 1.6), maximum total power (mean = 4.7) (SD = 0.5), maximum left foot power. (mean = 2.3) (SD = 0.3), maximum right foot power (mean = 2.4) (SD = 0.3), the power difference between left and right legs (mean = 8.5) (SD = 5.1), maximum power per kg (mean = 58.3) (SD = 8.9), the ratio between maximum jump and spin (average = 203.1) (SD = 70.6).

Table 2: Descriptive statistics for test performed on single two leg jump for age 20- 25 yrs

Age_Range		Mean	Std. Deviation
20-25 yrs	Single_two_leg_jump_EFI	99.0000	16.09348
	Single_two_leg_jump_V_max	2.8167	.11060
	Single_two_leg_jump_Height_min	-.2600	.08718
	Single_two_leg_jump_Jump_Height	.4900	.03606
	Single_two_leg_jump_Efficensy	82.0000	2.00000
	Single_two_leg_jump_Force_max_total	2.2800	.31321
	Single_two_leg_jump_Force_max_L	1.0667	.17926
	Single_two_leg_jump_Force_max_R	1.2167	.13317
	Single_two_leg_jump_diff_F_max	12.7333	6.90604
	Single_two_leg_jump_Force_max_rel	2.9067	.51033
	Single_two_leg_jump_Force_Diff_p_t1_t3	6.9667	1.55671
	Single_two_leg_jump_Power_max_total	4.6533	.55175
	Single_two_leg_jump_Power_max_L	2.2600	.28844

Single_two_leg_jump_Power_max_R	2.4133	.29501
Single_two_leg_jump_Power_diff_P_max	8.5333	5.10816
Single_two_leg_jump_Power_max_kg	58.2967	8.96663
Single_two_leg_jump_Power_h_max_h_min	203.1333	70.60611

Table 3 gives data for the age category +25 years; performance indicator by weight, (average 84 = 4) (SD = 17), maximum action speed (mean = 2.5) (SD = 0.2), jump height / min (average = 0.2) (SD = 0.04), jump height (mean = 0.4) (SD = 0.05), the efficiency of the jump (the power gained for the applied force) (average = 80) (SD = 11.2), total maximum force (average = 2.1) (SD = 0.3), maximum left foot force (mean = 1.1) (SD = 0.1), maximum right foot force (mean = 0.9) (SD = 0.4), the maximum force difference between left and right legs (mean = 2.4) (SD = 3.2), maximum relative strength (mean = 2.5) (SD = 0.2), the force difference p_{t1_t3} (mean = 4.2) (SD = 2.9), maximum total power (mean = 4.2) (SD = 0.9), maximum left foot power. (mean = 2.2) (SD = 0.4), maximum right foot power (mean = 2) (SD = 0.5), the power difference between left and right legs (mean = 5.1) (SD = 6.1), maximum power per kg (mean = 44.2) (SD = 19.9), the ratio between maximum jump and spin (mean = 175.3) (SD = 50.3).

Table 3: Descriptive statistics for test performed on single two leg jump for age 25+ yrs

Age_Range		Mean	Std. Deviation
25+ yrs	Single_two_leg_jump_EFI	84.4286	16.99860
	Single_two_leg_jump_V_max	2.5300	.24685
	Single_two_leg_jump_Height_min	-.2371	.04608
	Single_two_leg_jump_Jump_Height	.4014	.05984
	Single_two_leg_jump_Efficiency	80.0000	11.19524
	Single_two_leg_jump_Force_max_total	2.1186	.30765
	Single_two_leg_jump_Force_max_L	1.0671	.14326
	Single_two_leg_jump_Force_max_R	.8891	.35124
	Single_two_leg_jump_diff_F_max	2.3714	3.21803
	Single_two_leg_jump_Force_max_rel	2.5171	.22677
	Single_two_leg_jump_Force_Diff_p_t1_t3	4.2286	2.18687
	Single_two_leg_jump_Power_max_total	4.2443	.93357
	Single_two_leg_jump_Power_max_L	2.1757	.42003
	Single_two_leg_jump_Power_max_R	2.0843	.50023
	Single_two_leg_jump_Power_diff_P_max	5.1429	6.10133
	Single_two_leg_jump_Power_max_kg	44.2743	19.93489
	Single_two_leg_jump_Power_h_max_h_min	175.3286	50.33242

Table 4 represents the sigma value of the variables comparison for the three age groups of the parameters measured in the suction test.

Table 4: Comparison data by age category

ANOVA	Sig.
Single_two_leg_jump_EFI	Between Groups
	.119
	Within Groups
Single_two_leg_jump_V_max	Between Groups
	.167
	Within Groups
Single_two_leg_jump_Height_min	Between Groups
	.040
	Within Groups
Single_two_leg_jump_Jump_Height	Between Groups
	.062
	Within Groups
Single_two_leg_jump_Efficiency	Between Groups
	.963
	Within Groups
Single_two_leg_jump_Force_max_total	Between Groups
	.189
	Within Groups
Single_two_leg_jump_Force_max_L	Between Groups
	.181
	Within Groups
Single_two_leg_jump_Force_max_R	Between Groups
	.041
	Within Groups
Single_two_leg_jump_diff_F_max	Between Groups
	.033
	Within Groups
Single_two_leg_jump_Force_max_rel	Between Groups
	.034
	Within Groups
Single_two_leg_jump_Force_Diff_p_t1_t3	Between Groups
	.309
	Within Groups
Single_two_leg_jump_Power_max_total	Between Groups
	.589
	Within Groups
Single_two_leg_jump_Power_max_L	Between Groups
	.762
	Within Groups
Single_two_leg_jump_Power_max_R	Between Groups
	.408
	Within Groups

4. Discussion

The data from the study for comparison between age groups for maximum rate of action do not show significant changes (sig = 0.2), the jump height / min has significant changes (sig = 0.04), the height of the jump did not show significant changes (sig = 0.1), the efficiency of the jump (the power applied to the applied force) does not show significant changes (sig = 0.7), the total of maximum force does not show significant

changes (sig = 0.2), the maximum left foot force does not show significant changes (sig = 0.2), the maximum right foot force has significant changes (sig = 0.04), the maximum force difference between left and right legs is significant (sig = 0.03), the maximum relative strength has significant changes (sig = 0.03), the force difference $_p_t1_t3$ (sig = 0.3), the total of maximum power does not show significant changes (sig = 0.6), the maximum left foot power does not show significant changes (sig = 0.8), the maximum right foot power does not show significant changes (sig = 0.4). Bodybuilding is a sport in which competitors are judged on muscular appearance. Natural bodybuilders are drug-tested and are banned from the sport if caught using illegal substances. Appropriate preparation for a natural bodybuilding contest generally involves years of strength training followed by a "contest prep" in which the athlete focuses on dramatically reducing body fat to enhance muscular appearance. Thus, changes seen during competition preparation are not due to sudden dramatic elevations in volume, intensity, or frequency of resistance training but, rather, to a self-induced reduction in energy intake and increase in aerobic activity (Lambert et al., 2004). While other sports may involve short-term (eg, 7–21 d) weight-cutting strategies before competition, bodybuilding is unique in that prolonged (12+ wk) caloric restriction and increases in physical activity with physique-oriented goals are placed above fitness and physical-performance goals. Previous research on bodybuilders has mostly focused on the nutritional and body-compositional changes of the athletes. (Heyward et al., 1989; Walberg-Rankin et al., 1993; Brill & Keane 1994; Steen 1999). A few studies have examined other aspects of contest prep such as hormonal changes (Maestu et al., 2010; Maestu et al., 2008) and strength changes (Bamman et al., 1993). They provide valuable contributions to the bodybuilding literature, but much speculation and misinformation still exists. Most currently published case studies on bodybuilders (excepting the work by Steen focus on the well-known negative effects of anabolic steroid use or oil injections, creating an image of all bodybuilders as diseased, obsessed, steroid-injecting individuals. (Thorsteinsdottir et al., 2006; Koopman et al., 2005; Voelcker et al., 2010; Schafer et al., 2011; Mayr et al., 2012; Banke et al., 2012) . We believe there is more to bodybuilding than these profiles suggest. In addition to the physical changes accompanying bodybuilding preparation, little is known about how such a rigorous regimen may affect mood states. Changes in mood states have been observed after short-term intense exercise training, (Faude et al., 2009) but the effects of long-term bodybuilding preparation on mood states have not been characterized As body mass decreased, absolute VO_{2peak} and critical power decreased as expected while relative values for both remained fairly constant. In contrast, short-term weight cutting (ie, 1 wk) in other athletes may not have such a negative effect on physical performance (Marttinen et al., 2011). After competition, exercise abilities recovered rather slowly. Squat and deadlift strength and critical power recovered by month 4, while bench-press strength and AWC remained below baseline at month 6. This lack of strength and critical power/AWC recovery was reflected in continually depressed vigor as fatigue had returned to baseline by month.

In conclusion of this study results show that the maximum right foot force has significant changes (sig = 0.04), the maximum force difference between left and right legs is significant (sig = 0.03), the maximum relative strength has significant changes (sig = 0.03).

References

1. Astrand P. O., Rodahl K. Textbook of work physiology. New York: McGraw-Hill Book Company, 1986
2. Lambert C. P., Frank L. L., Evans WJ. Macronutrient considerations for the sport of bodybuilding. *Sports Med.* 2004;34(5):317–327. PubMed doi:10.2165/00007256-200434050-00004
3. Heyward V. H., Sandoval W. M., Colville B. C. Anthropometric, body composition and nutritional profiles of bodybuilders during training. *J Appl Sport Sci Res.* 1989;3(2):22–29.
4. Walberg-Rankin J., Edmonds C. E., Gwazdauskas F. C. Diet and weight changes of female bodybuilders before and after competition. *Int J Sport Nutr.* 1993;3(1):87–102. PubMed Natural Bodybuilding Case Study 591
5. Brill J. B., Keane M. W. Supplementation patterns of competitive male and female bodybuilders. *Int J Sport Nutr.* 1994;4(4):398–412. PubMed
6. Steen S. N. Precontest strategies of a male bodybuilder. *Int J Sport Nutr.* 1991;1(1):69–78. PubMed
7. Faude O., Meyer T., Urhausen A., et al. Recovery training in cyclists: ergometric, hormonal and psychometric findings. *Scand J Med Sci Sports.* 2009;19(3):433–441. PubMed doi:10.1111/j.1600-0838.2008.00795.x
8. Leveritt M., Abernethy P. Acute effects of high-intensity endurance exercise on subsequent resistance activity. . 1999;13:47-51.
9. Maestu J., Eliakim A., Jurimae J., et al. Anabolic and catabolic hormones and energy balance of the male bodybuilders during the preparation for the competition. *J Strength Cond Res.* 2010;24(4):1074–1081. PubMed doi:10.1519/JSC.0b013e3181cb6fd3
10. Maestu J., Jurimae J., Valter I., et al. Increases in ghrelin and decreases in leptin without altering adiponectin during extreme weight loss in male competitive bodybuilders. *Metabolism.* 2008;57(2):221–225. PubMed doi:10.1016/j.metabol.2007.09.004
11. Maughan R. J. Marathon running. In: Reilly T., Snell P., Williams C., et al., editors. *Physiology of sports.* London: Spon, 1969: 121-52
12. Bamman M. M., Hunter G. R., Newton L. E., et al. Changes in body composition, diet, and strength of bodybuilders during the 12 weeks prior to competition. *J Sports Med Phys Fitness.* 1993;33(4):383–391. PubMed

13. Thorsteinsdottir B., Grande J. P., Garovic V. D.. Acute renal failure in a young weight lifter taking multiple food supplements, including creatine monohydrate. *J Ren Nutr.* 2006;16(4):341–345. PubMed doi:10.1053/j.jrn.2006.04.025
14. Koopman M., Richter C., Parren R. J., et al. Bodybuilding, sesame oil and vasculitis. *Rheumatology (Oxford).* 2005;44(9):1135. PubMed doi:10.1093/rheumatology/keh712
15. Voelcker V., Sticherling M., Bauerschmitz J. Severe ulcerated ‘bodybuilding acne’ caused by anabolic steroid use and exacerbated by isotretinoin. *Int Wound J.* 2010;7(3):199–201. PubMed doi:10.1111/j.1742-481X.2010.00676.x
16. Schafer C. N., Guldager H, Jorgensen HL. Multi-organ dysfunction in bodybuilding possibly caused by prolonged hypercalcemia due to multi-substance abuse: case report and review of literature. *Int J Sports Med.* 2011;32(1):60–65. PubMed doi:10.1055/s-0030-1267200
17. Mayr F. B., Domanovits H, Laggner AN. Hypokalemic paralysis in a professional bodybuilder. *Am J Emerg Med.* 2012;30(7):1324.e5–1324.e 8. PubMed doi:10.1016/j.ajem.2011.06.029
18. Banke I. J., Prodinge P. M., Waldt S., et al. Irreversible muscle damage in bodybuilding due to long-term intramuscular oil injection. *Int J Sports Med.* 2012;33(10):829–834. PubMed doi:10.1055/s-0032-1311582
19. Miura A., Sato H., Whipp B. J., et al. The effect of glycogen depletion on the curvature constant parameter of the power-duration curve for cycle ergometry. *Ergonomics.* 2000;43(1):133–141. PubMed doi:10.1080/001401300184693
20. Marttinen R. H., Judelson D. A., Wiersma L. D., et al. Effects of self-selected mass loss on performance and mood in collegiate wrestlers. *J Strength Cond Res.* 2011;25(4):1010–1015. PubMed
21. Sporer B. C., Wenger H. A. Effects of aerobic exercise on strength performance following various periods of recovery. *J Strength Cond Res.* Nov 2003;17(4):638–644.
22. Widrick J. J., Costill D. L., Fink W. J., Hickey MS, McConell G. K., Tanaka H. Carbohydrate feedings and exercise performance: effect of initial muscle glycogen concentration. *J Appl Physiol.* Jun 1993;74(6):2998-3005

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).